

Supplementary Material for “High-Rate Free-Space Optical Communication with DMD-Based Modulating Retroreflectors”

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Abstract—This document provides a detailed design reference for the DMD-based modulating retroreflector (MRR) for free-space optical communication. It presents an optimal cat-eye retroreflector design, analyzes the ideal DMD-based implementation, compares available DMD modules, and details the specific DMD and system used in our experiments, including limitations and practical considerations.

I. CAT-EYE RETROREFLECTOR: OPTIMAL OPTICAL DESIGN

A cat-eye retroreflector is an optical configuration that returns incident light toward its source by focusing the incoming beam onto a mirror placed at the focal plane of a lens. For an optimal design of a cat-eye retroreflector, the mirror must follow the focal plane curvature of the lens, which is known as the Petzval field curvature [1] (Fig. 1a). This ensures that all incoming rays, regardless of their angle of incidence, will hit the mirror perpendicularly and get reflected along the same path, maximizing the angular acceptance and return efficiency. In this design, the lens focal length affects the system’s angular acceptance, with shorter focal lengths providing wider acceptance angles but increasing the alignment sensitivity. The lens aperture size also plays a crucial role, as it determines the amount of light collected, which can cut the incoming beam and increase the divergence of the returning beam. Key parameters such as lens focal length, aperture size, and mirror reflectivity determine the system’s angular acceptance and efficiency.

Fig. 1. Field curvature of the optimal cat-eye retroreflector optical path [2] and the ideal DMD-based implementation.

II. IDEAL DMD-BASED CAT-EYE RETROREFLECTOR

By replacing the mirror in the design with a digital micromirror device (DMD), the system can modulate the return beam. When using the DMD attitude control, each micromirror can be placed along the focal plane curvature (Fig. 1b), causing the reflected beam to be directed back toward the source, or at an angle that deflects the beam away, effectively modulating the return signal. In the ideal case, the DMD will follow the

curvature of the focal plane, with each mirror having a state in which it is perfectly parallel to the focal plane and another state for reflecting the light away, while also allowing control of each micromirror independently.

III. COMPARISON OF STATE-OF-THE-ART DMD MODULES

In practice, no such ideal DMD module exists, and different commercial DMDs have different specifications that affect their suitability for MRR applications. Most DMD modules are designed for projection applications, which allow for high-resolution control and individual micromirror addressing. However, they provide only two states for each micromirror (ON/OFF), which correspond to a predefined \pm tilt angle and do not allow the creation of a continuous reflection surface, as seen in Fig. 2a. This limitation introduces a significant loss in the return signal for most of the reflection angles, as only part of the incoming light is reflected toward the source efficiently, from the part of the mirrors that can be aligned with the focal plane curvature, causing the other mirrors to be even more out of focus (Fig. 2b). Another design of DMD modules is based on hexagonal micromirrors, which can be tilted in different directions, allowing the creation of a flat surface mirror. Such a surface can be approximated as the focal plane curvature, in the case of a relatively high focal length and small active area. But unfortunately, such commercially available DMD modules have a very low modulation rate, which will limit the MRR data rate.

Commercially available DMD modules are diverse, each with different pixel counts, window materials, and supported frame rates. Table I summarizes key parameters for representative devices.

Fig. 2. Illustration of different DMD surfaces allocation relative to the focal plane curvature.

Although the hexagonal micromirror design by Boston Micromachines (DM Hex-3066) allows for a flat mirror surface creation, which can be aligned better with the focal plane curvature of the lens Fig. 2a, the low modulation rate of a

Model	Pixels	Pixel Pitch	Max Rate	Tilt angles
TI DLP3010LC	1280 × 800	10.8 μm	32 kHz	±12°
TI DLP4500	912 × 1140	7.6 μm	62.5 kHz	±12°
TI DLP7000	1024 × 768	13.68 μm	80 kHz	±12°
TI DLP9500	1920 × 1080	10.8 μm	80 kHz	±12°
DM Hex-3066	3066 hexagonal mirrors	750 μm	10 kHz	0/0.45°

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF REPRESENTATIVE DMD MODULES.

single mirror of the device (10 kHz) limits its applicability for high-speed MRR communication, since this rate is significantly lower than the cutting-edge MRR rates in the hundreds of kHz to MHz range. But, since the development of these modules is still in progress, we might see improvements in their modulation rates in the future, outperforming traditional DMD modules for this MRR application while also providing better return efficiency.

Another module that can be used for a similar MRR design is a deformable mirror. Most such mirrors on the market are designed for spatial light modulation and consist of radial patterns. Some deformable mirror modules, such as those from Boston Micromachines [3], offer a pixelated surface that can be individually controlled to create a flat or curved mirror surface. By using such devices, the desired flat mirror surface can be created, which is then aligned with the focal plane curvature, allowing for a more accurate design than one using traditional DMD modules, which creates a tilted return surface. But these devices are also limited in their MEMS modulation rates, with their current maximum modulation rate being around 45 kHz, which is not better than the traditional DMD modules we have used in our experiments.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL DMD MODULE AND SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

In our experiment, a development kit for the DMD module was used, model AJD-4500-UT from Ajile [4], which is based on the DLP4500 DMD chip from Texas Instruments. This chip has a resolution of 912 × 1140 micromirrors, with a pixel pitch of 7.6 μm, and a maximum frame rate of 4.5 kHz for full-frame operation in binary mode (each mirror is in either a +12° or -12° tilt position). According to its datasheet, each micromirror can switch states (crossover time) in a nominal time of 5 μs, and, based on our rise and fall time measurements, the performance was even better. The actual rate limit, derived from the DMD switching time, which is nominally 16 μs, allows modulation rates up to 62.5 kbps, matching the device firmware rate limit we experienced.

A. Specific System Design

In our design (Fig. 3), the DMD is mounted at the focal plane of either a 50 mm or a 100 mm lens in a rigid mechanical assembly (Fig. 3a). The device supports preloaded sequences, which enabled us to load a PRBS7 sequence directly to the device memory and play it at maximum frame rate without requiring external control during operation. This feature was crucial for achieving high data rates, as external control through the standard interface is limited to a 1 kHz frame rate. By utilizing the preloaded sequence capability, we were

able to bypass this limitation and achieve the full 58 kbps data rate demonstrated in our experiments when using the first 16 rows in ROI mode.

Fig. 3. The design cross-section of the DMD-based modulating retroreflector system and photograph of the actual assembly.

The system achieved a 16-hour error-free transmission of PRBS7 sequence data at a rate of 58 kbps at laboratory conditions, yielding a BER of $< 3 \cdot 10^{-10}$. In outdoor experiments at 50 m distance, the system maintained a BER of $5.17 \cdot 10^{-7}$.

B. Angular Acceptance and Resolution Analysis

The design of the cat-eye retroreflector involves a critical trade-off between angular acceptance range and pointing accuracy requirements. In this work, we implemented and characterized two distinct assembly configurations using the same DMD module but with different focal length lenses. Both assemblies utilize a 1-inch aperture lens: the first uses a 50.0 mm focal length lens (Thorlabs LA4148), while the second uses a 100.0 mm focal length lens (Thorlabs LA4380).

The angular acceptance range of a cat-eye retroreflector is fundamentally determined by the DMD chip active area size ($h = 6.1614 \text{ mm} \times 9.855 \text{ mm}$) and the lens focal length (f). For the analysis, we use the shorter dimension ($h = 6.1614 \text{ mm}$) to calculate the conservative acceptance angle to match the scans shown in the paper (Fig. 2a). The acceptance angle can be approximated by the formula:

$$\theta_{\text{accept}} \approx 2 \arctan \left(\frac{h}{2f} \right) \quad (1)$$

For the 50.0 mm lens assembly, the full angular acceptance is $\theta_{\text{accept}} \approx 7.05^\circ$ (corresponding to $\pm 3.53^\circ$ half-angle). And for the 100.0 mm lens assembly, it is $\theta_{\text{accept}} \approx 3.53^\circ$ (corresponding to $\pm 1.77^\circ$ half-angle). The angular resolution, defined by the pointing accuracy of a single micromirror with pitch $p = 7.6 \text{ μm}$, can be calculated using the same formula. This yields $\theta_{\text{mirror}} \approx 0.0087^\circ$ for the 50.0 mm lens assembly and $\theta_{\text{mirror}} \approx 0.0044^\circ$ for the 100.0 mm lens assembly.

As expected, the 50.0 mm lens assembly with the shorter focal length provides approximately twice the acceptance angle compared to the 100.0 mm lens assembly, requiring less precise tracking of the interrogating beam. However, this comes at the cost of reduced angular resolution, which affects the pointing accuracy for directional control applications. The 100.0 mm lens assembly offers finer angular resolution but demands more accurate alignment and tracking systems. The choice between these configurations depends on the specific application requirements: the 50.0 mm lens assembly is more suitable for scenarios with limited tracking capability, while the 100.0 mm lens assembly is preferable when high angular precision is needed.

C. Performance at Different Angles of Incidence

As the main manuscript shows in Fig. 2, the reflected beam power barely changes within the acceptance angle of the MRR for both off and on states. This result is expected since each micromirror is modulated independently, and the DMD surface is designed to be perpendicular to the optical axis, which allows for a good approximation of the focal plane curvature for small active areas. Therefore, the link performance measured by the signal bit error rate (BER) is expected to be stable within the acceptance angle, as the return signal power remains relatively constant. Moreover, the highest-rate measurements, which used only 16 rows of the DMD active area required to achieve the 58 kbps modulation rate, were forced to be at the edge of the element. This limitation is caused by the device ROI configuration, which is limited to start from the first row, proving that at this rate, the system was not limited by the signal angle of incidence, but rather by the device communication bottleneck and measurement duration.

V. GROUND STATION ANALYSIS

As visualized in Fig. 1a of the main manuscript, the receiver optical path is designed to collect a 1-inch returning beam from the external port (EP) into the receiver fiber (DF). The beam is narrowed down by a 100 mm focal length lens (L4) and a 15.29 mm focal length lens (L5) to match the fiber collimator (FC2) specifications, which is then coupled into a multimode fiber with a 400 μm core diameter and 0.22 NA. This configuration provides a field of view (FOV) of 0.190° for the laboratory experiments.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{FOV} &= 2 \arctan \left(\frac{d_{\text{MM fiber}}}{2f_{\text{collimator}}} \right) \cdot \frac{f_{L5}}{f_{L4}} \\ &= 2 \arctan \left(\frac{400 \mu\text{m}}{2 \cdot 18.4 \text{ mm}} \right) \cdot \frac{15.29 \text{ mm}}{100.0 \text{ mm}} = 0.190^\circ \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

For the outdoor experiments, the beam was further expanded using a 150 mm focal length plano-convex lens (Thorlabs LA4874-B-ML) at the external port, followed by a 102 mm aperture, f/7 ED APO refractor telescope (TS-Optics, effective focal length = 714 mm). This additional telescope provides angular magnification for the system, resulting in a total receiver's field of view:

$$\text{FOV}_{\text{outdoor}} = \text{FOV}_{\text{lab}} \cdot \frac{f_{\text{LA4874}}}{f_{\text{telescope}}} = 0.190^\circ \cdot \frac{150 \text{ mm}}{714 \text{ mm}} = 0.034^\circ \quad (3)$$

The increased beam diameter at the outdoor setup allows for lower divergence for the transmitted beam and better collection efficiency, while the reduced FOV helps to mitigate background noise, which is crucial for maintaining a high signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) in outdoor conditions.

VI. SCALING TO SATELLITE APPLICATIONS

While our 50 m outdoor demonstration validates the technology under realistic atmospheric conditions and daylight background noise, scaling to satellite communication scenarios such as LEO applications would require system enhancements to accommodate the significantly increased link losses. For a representative 500 km LEO altitude, additional losses of approximately 20-40 dB (comprising free-space path loss scaling, extended atmospheric attenuation, and point-ahead angle geometric losses) for each direction would need to be addressed [5]. The system architecture provides clear pathways for such scaling: increasing the interrogating laser power from the current 1 mW to ~ 1 W provides a 30 dB improvement, and enlarging the ground station aperture from 102 mm can provide another improvement of more than 10 dB through increased collection area. In case extra power is needed, the ground station design can also be modified to transmit the carrier beam through a dedicated telescope, and by removing the 50:50 beam splitter from the optical path, an additional 6 dB improvement can be gained at the cost of requiring realignment for different distances and telescope configurations. Another potential change concerns the noise level, since a 780 nm laser is used in the current design, which is near the visible spectrum. Our experiments at low elevation angles are expected to have higher noise levels due to artificial light sources and reflected light from objects. In contrast, in space applications, the noise level is expected to be lower due to the absence of such sources or reflections, especially during nighttime operations. Our measured SNR of 36 dB at 50 m, combined with these scaling options and potential implementation of more sensitive detection techniques, provides a foundation for closing the link budget in LEO scenarios. The demonstrated technology performance and quantified system parameters enable informed link budget analyses for specific orbital applications, with the MRR architecture's inherent SWAP advantages becoming increasingly valuable for weight-constrained satellite platforms. As in most satellite FSO communication systems, our design implements only downlink (from satellite to ground) communication, which is the more demanding direction in terms of link budget. While the uplink can be implemented using a more conventional approach based on radio-frequency (RF) communication, FSO can also be used for the uplink. As in traditional FSO communication systems, it can be implemented using a dedicated laser transmitter on the ground station and a photodetector on the satellite, with a dedicated wavelength in a wavelength-division multiplexing (WDM) configuration to separate the uplink and downlink signals. But this design also allows for a half-duplex implementation by modulating the transmitted carrier beam. In this implementation, the satellite can also measure the incoming beam (additional receiver hardware is required

for this implementation) for uplink communication, while modulating the reflected beam for downlink communication. Since the same beam is used for both directions, both terminals cannot modulate data at the same time, and half-duplex logic must be implemented as a time-division multiplexing (TDM) scheme, where the satellite alternates between transmitting and receiving modes, allowing for bidirectional communication without the need for separate laser sources for uplink and downlink.

VII. SUMMARY

As shown in this section, there are very different DMD modules with different specifications available in the market, but none of them is ideal for MRR applications, and each one has its own limitations. While the presented design can support all modules, the system performance will change according to the specific module used. The suitable DMD module should be chosen based on the required modulation rate, return efficiency, and angular accuracy for the specific MRR application.

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